

THE ACTIVITY OF THE COMMITTEE IMPLEMENTING CONSTITUTIONAL CONTROL IN KARAKALPAKSTAN AND ITS LEGAL FRAMEWORK.

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Annotation. This article analyzes the activities of the committee responsible for constitutional control in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, its legal foundations, and powers. Additionally, the legal and political significance of constitutional control, the committee's role within the state governance system, and its role in protecting the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are highlighted. The legal framework of the committee's activities, its decisions, and their social impact are also examined. The article identifies factors contributing to the committee's effective functioning through current legislation and practical examples.

Keywords: Republic of Karakalpakstan, constitutional control, Constitution, committee activities, state governance, legal system, rule of law.

As long as a state has a Constitution, it is of great importance to ensure its observance and to take special measures regarding the compliance of all normative-legal acts developed and adopted by all state bodies with the Constitution.

In turn, such responsibilities are assigned to the Constitutional Control Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In particular, Article 2 of the Law "On the Constitutional Control Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan" dated June 12, 2021, defines the legal status of the Constitutional Control Committee and provides the following definition: "Constitutional control in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is carried out by the Constitutional Control Committee. The Constitutional Control Committee is a state body responsible for supervising the compliance of legislative acts adopted by the legislative and executive authorities with the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan."

Furthermore, Article 1 of the Regulations of the Constitutional Control Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan dated February 10, 2023, outlines the legal status and functions of the Committee as follows: "Constitutional control in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is exercised by the Constitutional Control Committee. The function of the Constitutional Control Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is to monitor the compliance of

legislative acts adopted by the legislative and executive authorities with the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.”

A comparison of Article 2 of the Law “On the Constitutional Control Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan” and Article 1 of the Committee’s Regulations shows that in both documents the legal status of the Constitutional Control Committee is clearly defined. This establishes that the Committee’s primary function is to supervise the conformity of legislative acts of the legislative and executive authorities with the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and that it is responsible for this task.

A similar norm is reflected in Article 132 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which states: “The Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan considers cases regarding the compliance of legislative and executive authority documents with the Constitution.” In addition, this norm is enshrined in the Law “On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated April 27, 2021.

Specifically, Article 3 of this law defines the status of the Constitutional Court of Uzbekistan as follows: “The Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a permanent judicial authority that considers cases regarding the compliance of legislative and executive authority documents with the Constitution.” As can be seen, all the cited legal acts clearly define the legal status of the constitutional control body, and based on that, its main function is to consider cases concerning the compliance of legislative and executive authority documents with the Constitution.

Unlike this, in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Constitution does not specify such a legal status and corresponding functions at the constitutional level for the Constitutional Control Committee, which is the constitutional control body in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In particular, Article 112 of the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan states: “Constitutional control in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is carried out by the Constitutional Control Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.” As can be seen, the Constitutional Control Committee is generally defined as the body that carries out constitutional control, but it does not explicitly state that its supervision is primarily concerned with cases regarding the compliance of legislative and executive authority documents with the Constitution.

In this regard, introducing such clarity would be appropriate to clearly define the position of the Constitutional Control Committee within the state

authority system of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and, based on that, to determine the legal status and relations of the Committee with the legislative and executive authorities.

Accordingly, it is advisable to supplement part 1 of Article 112 of the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with the following new wording: "Constitutional control in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is carried out by the Constitutional Control Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The Constitutional Control Committee considers cases regarding the compliance of legislative and executive authority documents with the Constitution." In turn, the Constitutional Control Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan exercises the following powers:

First, upon the instruction of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, it issues opinions on the compliance of draft laws and other documents submitted to the Supreme Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan;

Second, upon proposals from at least one-fifth of the deputies of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan or the Chairman of the Supreme Council, it submits conclusions on the compliance of laws and other documents adopted by the Supreme Council with the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan to the Supreme Council;

Third, upon the instruction of the Supreme Council, it submits conclusions on the compliance of the decisions of the Presidium of the Supreme Council and orders of the Chairman of the Supreme Council with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Karakalpakstan;

Fourth, based on the instructions of the Supreme Council, proposals from at least one-fifth of the deputies of the Supreme Council, or the Chairman of the Supreme Council, it submits conclusions on the compliance of decisions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Karakalpakstan to the Supreme Council.

Additionally, the Constitutional Control Committee has the right, on its own initiative, to submit conclusions on the compliance of documents of the highest state authorities and administration of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

The Committee's conclusions may only be annulled by a decision of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan adopted by a two-thirds majority vote of all deputies of the Supreme Council.

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